

Intestate Succession in Statutory Marriages of Persons Subject to Customary Law in Nigeria: Revisiting Cole v. Cole, Contexts and Limits

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Abstract:

The legal principle upon which intestate succession in statutory marriage is predicated is that distribution of the estate should be in accordance with English law because the statutory marriage clothed the parties with a new status different from customary law. This principle used to be contained in the Marriage Ordinance and was given judicial authority in *Cole v Cole*. The decision in *Cole* has been followed in a wide variety of cases and the simple requirement for its application has been the intestate death of a person who has contracted a statutory marriage. While *Cole* involved a single statutory marriage, It has been applied in cases where there were in addition to the statutory marriage, wives and issues of customary marriage. The restriction of right of succession to only the issues of the statutory marriage has resulted in the denial of the valid rights of these other children. This paper sought to achieve two objectives, to wit: to examine the principle laid down in *Cole v Cole* and analyse the limits of its applications within the context of current legal framework for statutory marriage and administration of estate in Nigeria. It was found that while *Cole v Cole* remains a valid authority, its peculiar facts make it most appropriate to apply it in cases involving single statutory marriages. Its application in cases where there are other valid customary marriages in addition to the statutory marriage has often resulted in inequitable results. Hence, the advocacy for such cases to be decided using conflict of laws rules. It was therefore recommended that there is need for legislative intervention, which will codify the principles of conflict of laws applicable to intestate succession in multiple marriages and provide a proper context for the application of *Cole's* case as judicial authority.

Keywords: Cole v. Cole, Statutory Marriage, Customary Marriage, Nigeria, Estates, Personal Law. Intestate Succession.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Succession has always been an integral aspect of every society hence there is hardly any society or legal culture without a well-articulated framework for succession. With the emergence of multi-culturalism, trans-cultural and trans-national migration, a well ingrained principle that is recognized across the world's legal system is the fact that the law that should govern succession to a man's property is the law of the place of his origin (personal law). Thus, where a person dies far away from the place of his ancestry, the courts would still make the effort to identify what his personal law is and apply it in the distribution of his estate.

Due to the biological connection in the determination of personal law, it enjoys a level of permanence and certainty that stands it apart from other classes of law which apply to individuals, so long as they are within the geographical area within which it applies. Thus, a person's personal law would accompany him throughout his life unless there is a conscious decision by the individual to renounce his ancestral personal law and adopt another system of personal law.

In Africa and by implication Nigeria where personal law is determined by tribal connections, it is highly unusual for individuals to change their personal law. In fact, personal law used to be perceived as immutable (Mbeng and Ntonga, 2020) and the general rule until recently was that "a person cannot shed one customary law in favour of another" (Mbeng and Ntonga, 2020). It can be argued that this principle could have been absolutely true in pre-colonial Nigeria. The introduction of colonial rule introduced new dynamics in cultural patterns of association and interaction of the people of Nigeria. Colonial rule not only resulted in the introduction of the English system of government, trade and justice; it also resulted in the introduction of English cultural practices particularly those relating to religion. One major consequential effect of this was the introduction of the English or statutory marriage or what is sometimes also called Christian marriage. While hitherto, a marriage was universally regarded as a union of a man and a woman, in order to create a family, the major distinction in the English, statutory, or Christian marriage which differentiates it from African customary marriage is its monogamous nature (*Hyde v. Hyde*, 1866).

It was this fundamental difference between customary marriage and Christian or statutory marriage that prompted the assumption that once an African contracts a statutory marriage, it serve as an indication of a decision to adopt a new pattern of life that is diametrically different from the culture into which they were born. This singular decision was deemed sufficient to indicate an acquisition of a new status and by implication a change of personal law. This perspective was given judicial approval in *Cole v. Cole*.

While *Cole v. Cole* is regarded as a *locus classicus* (Bankas, 1992), its novelty is not without some level of notoriety. This can be seen in the fact that Tobi (1996) in his textbook on Nigeria Legal System introduced it as: "the notorious *Cole v. Cole*". Its notoriety can be attributed to the fact that not long after the decision in *Cole v. Cole*, its

capacity for inequity began to emerge in cases like *Smith vs. Smith* (1924), *Adegbola v. Folaranmi* (1921), *Gooding vs. Martin* (1942), and *Coleman vs. Shang* (1959).

In all of these cases, arguments had been made to exclude other children aside those that were born out of the statutory marriages, thereby depriving them of their legitimate rights to inherit from the estate of their parent. The perceived inequitable decisions, thus prompted calls for limitations to the application of the rule in *Cole v. Cole*.

In spite of the challenges that have arisen in the application, *Cole v. Cole* continues to be a cornerstone of Nigerian jurisprudence on the effect of Christian or statutory marriage on the status of Nigerians.

Despite significant changes to Nigerian laws, particularly the Marriage Act and Administration of Estate Law, *Cole v. Cole* has continued to be applied as judicial authority across Nigeria without a proper reference to the context in which it was decided, particularly the law(s) upon which it was decided and significant amendments that since been made to Nigerian laws on marriage and succession.

This paper therefore seeks to answer one single question to wit: can *Cole v. Cole* be applied in all parts of Nigeria as judicial authority? And secondly, if it can be applied generally in intestate succession of persons who have contracted a marriage under the Act.

Towards the realization of these objectives, this paper will be broken into the following parts:

- a. Review of *Cole v. Cole*.
- b. Challenges and limitations in the application of *Cole v. Cole*.
- c. Examination of current legal framework for statutory marriage and succession in Nigeria.
- d. Proper context for the application of *Cole vs. Cole*.

2. LEGAL MATERIALS AND METHODS

In discussing the issues of intestate succession of persons who have contracted statutory marriages and the limits of *Cole v. Cole*, a doctrinal methodology was adopted. Primary sources such as the Marriage Act, 1970, The Administration of Estate Law of Kwara and Lagos States were relied on. In addition, relevant judicial authorities were used and reliance was placed on older decisions of the court where there are no modern judicial decisions. There is a shortage of academic materials on this topic; however, the available relevant ones were consulted.

3. REVIEW OF COLE v. COLE

William Cole, a Nigerian man, native of the then Lagos colony conducted a statutory marriage in Sierra Leone. He subsequently died intestate leaving behind his widow, Mary and a son, Alfred. The deceased brother sought to be declared the customary heir to the deceased's estate, arguing that under the Yoruba customary law, he was the rightful heir

and trustee. His application was initially granted by the court of first instance based on the provisions of S. 19 of the Supreme Court Ordinance, 1876.

Mary J. Cole, however appealed the decision and the court re-convened as a full court and the decision of trial court was overturned. It was then held that customary law ought not to be have applied in determining the case, rather the question of who ought to be declared the heir ought to have been determined using English Law of succession. The basis of this decision was that although William Cole as a native of Lagos was ordinarily subject to customary law but by contracting a Christian marriage, he had acquired a new status which was alien to customary law and his property therefore ought not to be shared under Customary Law but in accordance with English Law. In the famous dictum of Griffith J., he noted that due to the distinct differences between customary marriages and Christian or statutory marriages, the parties and the offspring of Christian marriages were clothed with a status unknown to native law.

According to him, Christian marriage imposes on the husband, duties and obligations not recognised by native law. In addition, the wife in a Christian marriage has greater financial involvement in the marriage because on getting married, a wife's property becomes that of the husband. He further noted that parties to Christian marriages are usually educated and enlightened persons such as doctors, barristers, clergy men and even Bishops and to subject their spouses to elements of customary succession would result in clear inequity.

4. DISCUSSION OF COLE v. COLE

Although the case is often cited as 'legal authority for the principle that where a person who contracts a marriage under the Marriage Ordinance dies intestate, his estate should be distributed in accordance with the English rules of intestate succession. This principle is already a well-established principle contained in the Marriage Ordinance, and subsequently in the Marriage Act (1958). S 36 of the Marriage Act provides:

(1) Where any person who is subject to native law or custom contracts a marriage in accordance with the provision of this Act and such person dies intestate, subsequently to the commencement of this act, leaving a widow or husband, or any issue of such marriage; and also where any person who is the issue of any such marriage as aforesaid dies intestate subsequently to the commencement of the Act:-

The personal property of such intestate and also any real property of which the said intestate might have disposed by will shall be distributed in accordance with the provisions of the law of England relating to the

distribution of the personal estate of intestates, any native law or custom to the contrary notwithstanding,

Provided that

(a) Where by the law of England any portion of the estate of such intestate would become a portion of the casual hereditary revenues of the Crown, such portion shall be distributed in accordance with the provisions of native law and custom and shall not become a portion of the said casual hereditary revenues; and

(b) Real property, the succession to which cannot by native law and custom be affected by testamentary disposition, shall descend in accordance with the provisions of such native law or custom, anything herein to the contrary notwithstanding.

Due to the fact that the case was instituted in Lagos, the court could not apply the marriage Ordinance of Nigeria. In deciding what should be the applicable law under which succession to the estate be determined, the principle that was adopted was that contained in the Supreme Court Ordinance, now replicated in the High Court Laws (2006) that where a transaction is one that is unknown to customary law, customary law should not apply.

It is instructive to note that in most texts and academic studies on the case, it is usually examined within the context of effect of statutory marriages conducted outside the colony Agbede (1991), and the law applicable to transactions unknown to customary law Tobi (1996), Park (1963). While older texts critically examined the contexts of the decision and were able to conceptualise the limits of its application particularly in relation to the fact that it was more appropriate as authority for statutory marriages conducted outside Nigeria, more recent texts have tended to generalize the application of the case. For example, Koni (2021) while discussing *Cole v. Cole*, stated as follows:

The rule in this case is that a native who undergoes Christian marriage rites outside his domicile will be deemed to have intended that succession to his property should be governed by the English law of succession, rather than the native customary law. It is submitted that the same rule will even apply presently where the Christian marriage rites are conducted within jurisdiction under the Marriage Act.

Based on the principle of law on which the case was decided and the outright inapplicability of the Marriage Ordinance or Act to the case, it has been suggested by bringing the facts of the case under the principle of transactions unknown to customary law, marriage was treated as a transaction. However, even within this context, English law ought to have applied to only those incidents that arose *inter vivos* such as divorce. It has been noted that even though marriage is a contract, it can be regarded as a transaction “but only with respect to *inter-vivos* incidents of marriage such as divorce” Kasumu (1964).

Post-mortem incidents such as succession therefore, ought to not ordinarily be regarded as part of the transaction. This is because “the dispute’ when it relates to marriage and succession will rarely involve the direct parties, that is the spouses *in terse* Salacuse (1964). This restriction has however been circumvented by treating marriage as a *sui generis* transaction. Salacuse (1964), also observed that succession will be treated as an inherent incidence of marriage and it will be governed by the same law that governed the statutory marriage. Dickson and Rene (2020), in a similar way also noted that succession rights become enforceable because the “statutory marriage works a transformation of the status of the spouses and creates extensive legal consequences affecting not only them but their children and relatives as well.”

Based on the legal principles upon which *Cole v. Cole* was decided, it has been viewed as more appropriate to conceive it as an authority for the inherent incidence theory rather than in the context in which it has mostly been relied on by courts as a legal authority for the principle that a statutory marriage has a transformative effect on the personal law of a person who has contracted such a marriage and as a result, intestate succession to his estate would be automatically governed by English Law.

5. LEGAL CONSEQUENCES OF COLE V. COLE AND LIMITS OF ITS APPLICATION

Generally, the rules of succession are designed to give effect to the intentions of the deceased and protect the interests of those who are legitimately entitled to inherit from them. That simple objective it would appear also motivated the court in *Cole v. Cole*, where the well-stated intent of the judges indicated their primary objective was to protect the interest of the wife and son of the deceased, William Cole. What can be said to have made this easy was the fact that the legitimate heir was the spouse and child of the statutory marriage. If this context is treated as a material fact, it would have meant that *Cole v. Cole* cannot be used as authority in cases where there are other heirs aside the children of the statutory or Christian marriage.

It is from the controversies created in these subsequent cases that *Cole v. Cole* derived much of its notoriety and capacity to result in inequitable results. Some of these cases will be examined in this section.

5.1 Adegbola v. Folaranmi (1921)

The facts of the case were that the deceased, Johnson had in his youth gotten married under customary law. He was later sold into slavery and taken to Trinidad, British West Indies. There he married Mary in the Catholic Church. After forty years in the West Indies, he returned to Nigeria and re-connected with his first wife and child from the first marriage.

The child visited him regularly while he was still alive. He died intestate in 1900 and his wife, through the statutory marriage, died in 1918. She however left a will declaring the defendant as her executor. The plaintiff, the only daughter of the deceased then applied to be granted ownership of the house as the only child of the original owner and his heir under customary law. The claim of the plaintiff, Adegbola was rejected at the trial court, and the decision was affirmed on appeal by the Nigerian Supreme Court.

The court affirmed the decision of the trial court on the following grounds:

1. That Johnson and Mary had contracted a valid Christian Marriage in Trinidad and the courts in Nigeria are bound to recognize the marriage.
2. That the Christian Marriage, although subsequent to the local customary marriage of the plaintiff's mother and Johnson, was valid despite the fact that it contravened the marriage ordinance of 1884 which prohibited a person who is married under customary law from contract a Christian marriage. It was held that this provision did not apply to this marriage because it was contracted prior to the enactment of the marriage ordinance in 1884.
3. That English law should apply to the distribution of the estate of Johnson and that since the plaintiff was not the legitimate child of the statutory marriage, she was disentitled to inherit her father's house.

5.2 Goodings v. Martin (1942)

In this case, the deceased had first contracted a statutory marriage with the mother of the plaintiff. After her death, he contracted a customary marriage with the mother of the defendants. In determining who was entitled to inherit his estate, the court held that since the plaintiff was the only child of the deceased through the statutory marriage, he was the only one that was entitled to inherit and all others are thereby precluded.

The decisions in these two cases have drawn criticism. Bankas, commented that the courts misconstrued the issues and mechanically applied English law, and thus disinherited and bastardized children that were legitimate by African standards, Bankas (1996). Similar sentiments had also been earlier expressed by Salacuse (1964). He had opined that in the cases of *Adegbola and Goodings*, the court failed to take cognizance of the fact that the statutory marriage did not result in an absolute change of status, and that the change of status only related to matters that are incidental to the statutory marriage, particularly succession. By deeming that statutory marriages resulted in a complete change of status, which made English law applicable to transactions that had been entered into prior to the statutory marriage and after the statutory, which are otherwise equally

legitimate under the personal law of the deceased, the court had laid down a principle not supported by law that once a person who is normally subject to customary law contracts a Christian marriage, his personal law changes.

There are other distinctions between *Cole v. Cole* and *Adegbola* and *Goodings* cases which, if it taken into consideration by the court, might have resulted in different decisions. These include the following:

- a. In *Adegbola's* case, the customary marriage preceded the statutory marriage. The child of the customary marriage therefore had a subsisting right which pre-dated that statutory marriage and which the statutory marriage ought not to have extinguished. By holding that only the spouse of the statutory marriage was the legitimate heir, the position amounts to holding that the subsequent marriage invalidated the legitimacy of the plaintiff, whose mother was properly married under customary law. It is significant to note that even under the current legal regime for statutory marriage, customary marriage is not regarded as having a lower status to a marriage under the Act and a person who is already validly married under customary law is prohibited from contracting a statutory marriage with another person. The subsequent statutory marriage is regarded as invalid (Marriage Act, 1958).
- b. Also in *Gooding's* case, the customary marriage had been contracted after the death of the deceased's first wife with whom he had contracted a statutory marriage. By the death of the wife, the deceased had the capacity to contract the statutory marriage and the prohibition of the deceased contracting a subsequent marriage could be effective only while his wife was still alive.

It can be inferred that by contracting a marriage under customary law, the deceased at that material time saw himself as being governed under customary law and by all implications can be said to have abandoned the earlier status acquired while being married in the Christian marriage. If that contract or transaction has therefore ended with the death of his first wife, should the rule of that marriage apply to the second marriage, which by all intent were intended to be governed by a different set of laws?

6. DISTINGUISHING AND LIMITING *COLE v. COLE*

Although *Cole v. Cole* remains the most decisive authority on intestate succession in statutory marriages, in recognition of the differences in the material facts of the case from subsequent cases, and to prevent some of the unsavoury consequences of its application in cases where the facts are not exactly the same such as the situation that arose in *Adegbola* and *Goodings*, several attempts have been made to limit the application of *Cole v. Cole*. In cases decided after it, where the facts also bothered on intestate succession in statutory marriages, limits were set to its authority through the process of distinguishing or distinction.

The most important point used as a basis of this was to classify Cole as case involving a single statutory marriage and set it apart from cases involving Africans who has contracted a statutory marriage concurrently with a customary marriage with another person and or when the statutory marriage is contracted after a customary marriage or when a customary marriage is contracted after a statutory marriage ends.

Three important cases will be examined in this regard. They are *Asiata Onikepe v. Goncallo*, (1900); *Re Adadevoh* (1951) and *Coleman v Sheng* (1959).

6.1 Asiata v. Goncallo (Manner of Life Theory)

The facts of this case were that the deceased, a Yoruba man had been enslaved in his youth and taken to Brazil. While in Brazil, he married a woman according to Islamic rights and later celebrated the same marriage according to Christian rights. He had two daughters from the first marriage. Upon his emancipation, he returned to Nigeria and married another woman during the subsistence of the first marriage under customary law. The second marriage was blessed with only one child. When the deceased died, his daughter from the second marriage instituted an action for a share of the estate.

Her prayers were initially refused by the trial court which held that English law ought to be applied in the distribution of the estate. On appeal to the full court however, the judgment of the trial court was set-aside. The appellate court up-held the validity of the second marriage and held that Islamic law can be used in the distribution of the estate.

The court justified its decision through the manner of life theory. It referred to the fact that although the parties to the case had contracted a statutory marriage, their intention through their manner of life did not indicate they had intended to be bound by the rules governing statutory marriage or its consequences. The court per Griffith J, had held that looking at the deceased's manner of life, it would be wrong to apply any law other than Islamic law which had governed the entirety of the deceased's life. He evidenced their manner of life by the fact that the deceased's first wife whom he married in accordance with Christian rites had not, based on available facts raised any objection to her husband's subsequent marriage.

The rationale behind the court's decision was also summarized by Salacuse (1964). He noted that by making reference to the manner of life lived by the deceased, the court demonstrated the importance of applying the law which most reflects the deceased's expectations and living habits in the distribution of their estate when they die intestate. Salacuse (1964).

6.2 In Re Sarah I. Adadevoh and Ten Ors v. Herbert Samuel Heelas Macaulay (1951) (Conflict of Law Theory)

The principles of conflict of laws were extensively adopted in this case to determine the appropriate interpretation of s. 36 of the Marriage Ordinance, which had provided that:

When a person subject to native law and custom contracts a marriage in accordance with the provisions of the Ordinance and such a person dies intestate...leaving a widow or husband or any issue of such a marriage; and also where any issue of such a marriage aforesaid dies intestate...the property of such an intestate and also any real property of which the intestate might have disposed by will, shall be distributed in accordance with the provisions of the Law of England relating to the distribution of the personal estate of intestate, any native law or custom to the contrary notwithstanding.

The facts of the case were that the deceased had contracted a statutory marriage in 1898. His wife in that marriage died in 1899 and the marriage had no issue. The deceased at various times before and after the statutory marriage had children with several women; the appellants were the children of these liaisons. The court found as fact that four of these women were married to the deceased under customary law. The trial court had initially found that the appellants were not entitled to any part of the estate and that they would only become eligible if there are no other next of kin and the estate would escheat to the Crown.

It was argued on behalf of the appellant that the correct position as contained in Halsbury's Law of England (1907), is that legitimacy of children which serves as basis of succession is a question of status and it is to be determined by the law of the domicile. It was also argued on their behalf that the clause 'any native law to the contrary' in s.36 of the Marriage Ordinance relates to distribution of the estate and not to the right of succession which is determined by the status of the claimants. The court in giving its decision first referred to its earlier decision in *Re Adeline Subulade Williams* (1941), where it had held that a person, whose rights depend on customary law and not English law, is excluded from succession on the intestate death of a person who is the product of a statutory marriage. It held that the implication of that decision is that the widow of an intestate and his children though lawful by the law of the domicile were to be left destitute and that such a decision would not be giving effect to 'common sense and decency.' The court also held that important cases such as *Re Goodman's Trusts* (1889), and *Sinha Peerage Case* (1946) were not cited to the court and were not considered by it in reaching its earlier decision. The court concluded that there was need to depart from its earlier decision which was reached *per incuriam* so as to avoid the decision continuing to 'inflict hardship and injustice upon generations in the future'.

6.3 Coleman v. Shang (The Conflict of Laws Theory)

This is another important case which has significantly shaped existing jurisprudence in relation to the intestate succession to the estate of a person who has contracted a statutory marriage. The facts of the case demonstrate the fluidity with which natives oscillated between marrying under customary law as well as under statute.

In the case, the deceased had married his first wife, Adeline Johnson under the customary law and they had three children. When she died, the deceased married again and the second marriage was contracted under the Marriage Ordinance. The second marriage produced five children. The second wife also died in 1940. During the continuance of the statutory marriage, the deceased cohabited with the appellant, who had ten children for him. After the death of the second wife, he again contracted another marriage, this time under customary law. The deceased eventually died intestate. The respondent who was the only surviving children of the second marriage, applied for letters of administration on the ground that he was the only child of the deceased that was qualified to succeed him. The trial court relying on *Cole v. Cole* decided in his favour. This judgement was however aside on appeal.

The Ghana Court of Appeal in deciding the appropriate law that should govern the estate of the deceased limited the application of *Cole v. Cole*.

Two points stand out in the rationale given by the court. These are:

1. That s. 48 (1) of the Marriage Ordinance of Ghana (1884) which provided that the phrase “leaving a widow, a husband or any issue of such marriage” merely indicates the condition precedent upon which English Law will be applied to the estate of an intestate who married under the ordinance. They do not limit the class of those entitled to share in his estate.
2. Another significant point that was raised by the court related to those who would be qualified to inherit under the Statute of Distribution of England (1670). The court held that “wife and child” should be interpreted to mean lawful wife and lawful child by any law of domicile, and not by the law of England.

This court in this case applied a well-established principle of conflict of laws that legitimacy of children is determined by the law of the domicile of the father, *Agbede* (1989).

7. RELEVANCE OF COLE vs. COLE IN CONTEMPORARY TIMES IN NIGERIA

The importance of *Cole v. Cole* to the development of the jurisprudence of Nigerian or West African Family Law cannot be over-estimated. While it has set down a framework for recognizing the unique rights arising from statutory marriages, its application to instances where the deceased contracted customary marriages prior to the statutory marriage or upon the dissolution or demise of the spouses of the statutory marriage has resulted in complex situations whereby the children of the statutory marriage while

relying on *Cole v. Cole* have sought to exclude the other children from the estate of their parents. Although the exclusion of customary law will be justified where the deceased contracted only a statutory marriage, its application to multi-tiered marriages usually results in unfair exclusion of children other than those of the statutory marriage.

This exclusion has been the basis for the inequity that arises when *Cole v. Cole* is regarded as a general authority for all instances where a person who contracts a statutory marriage dies intestate. Thus, many decades after, *Cole v. Cole* is still treated as the gospel as evident in most of the recent authorities of the Supreme Court such as *Obusez v. Obusez* (2007) and *Salubi v. Nwariakwu* (2003).

Meanwhile, the Privy Council decision in *Coleman v. Sheng* (1959) provided for the context for the application of *Cole v. Cole*. However, lower courts have continued to misapply the reasoning in *Cole v. Cole*, often applying same without any limits or conditions. For example, in *Mohammed v. Mohammed* (2022), the Shariah Court of Appeal of Kwara State denied the rights of the plaintiffs to their father's estate, outrightly excluding customary law notwithstanding the fact that the decisions in both *Asiata v Goncalo* (1900) and *Coleman v Sheng* (1959) which are exceptions to the strict application of *Cole v. Cole* would have availed them. A similar decision was reached in *In the Estate of Late Dr. Sa'ad Usman Sarkin Jere, kaduna State Suit no. KDH/KAD/484/2021* following the same pattern with Mohammed's case.

It is evident therefore that adequate regards have not been had to the cases which can be regarded as exceptions to the general principles espoused in *Cole v. Cole*, and the case continues to be erroneously regarded as the overriding authority notwithstanding the existence of context which would have made other authorities like *Coleman v. Sheng* and *Re Adadevoh* more appropriate. Thus, it is pertinent to situate *Cole v. Cole* in its proper context so that courts can be properly guided when applying it.

Multi-tiered marriages are still a common feature in Nigerian society; thus strict categorization of marriages into polygamous or statutory marriages has not been achieved as people contract statutory, religious and customary marriages simultaneously. Therefore, the assumption that a statutory marriage is proof of intention to be bound by the English law is not conclusive particularly where the same individual goes ahead to contract other marriages under the customary law.

In addition, academic writings have followed the pattern espoused by the courts, for example, Ajibola (2024), Akingboye and Kolade-Fasuyi (2024) and Koni (2021). To this end, examining the current legal framework and the extent to which they have changed from the state of the law when *Cole v. Cole* was decided becomes important.

8. EXAMINATION OF THE CURRENT LEGAL FRAMEWORK FOR STATUTORY MARRIAGE AND SUCCESSION IN NIGERIA

8.1 Marriage Act

The Marriage Act (2004), which replaced the Marriage Ordinance (1958) is the law regulating statutory marriage and by implication Christian marriage. The marriage which formed the basis of *Cole v. Cole* was not celebrated in Lagos but in Sierra Leone. It is on this ground that it was classified as a foreign statutory marriage, Diala (2014).

This made S.36 of the Marriage Ordinance of Nigeria which provided that the estate of person who had contracted a marriage under the Marriage Ordinance should be distributed in accordance with English Law inapplicable to the case.

However, even if the marriage had been celebrated in the Colony of Lagos, a significant point that has always been highlighted is the fact that the Marriage Ordinance of 1958 was only applicable to Lagos and not throughout Nigeria, as noted by Agbede (1991). It is also important to note that under the present Marriage Act, s. 36 has been removed. The implication of this is that the clause excluding the application of customary law in intestate succession is no longer a part of the Marriage Act. However, the application of this principle is retained in some states in Nigeria through the Administration of Estate Law, where provisions identical to S. 36 are provided for.

8.2. Administration of Estate Law

It is important to note that there are significant differences in the content of the administration of Estate Laws of states in Nigeria.¹ In the Administration of Estate Law of Kwara State for example, S.1 first provides for exclusionary clause. Thus:

S.1, This law shall not apply:

- a. To deaths occurring before its commencement unless otherwise provided; or
- b. To the estates of deceased persons, the administration of which is governed by Islamic Law.

It goes ahead to provide in

S.1 (2) for the person whose estate can be subject to Administration of Estate. It is provided thus:

1(2) The provisions of this law relating to the administration of the estate of a person who died intestate or the undisposed part of the estate of a testator shall apply only to persons who contract a valid monogamous marriage and are survived by a spouse or issue of such marriage.

¹ There are 36 states in Nigeria each of different states have their Administration of Estate Law. Although they are fundamentally the same, there are minor differences.

This section can be interpreted as not amounting to a mandatory rule but only a condition precedent for the application of Administration of Estates Law.

The prescriptive nature of the provisions of S.1 (2) can be contrasted with the provisions of S.49 (5) of the Administration of Estate Law of Lagos, which replicated precisely the erstwhile provisions of S.36 of the Marriage Ordinance 1958. The implication of this is that absolute exclusion of customary law only applies in Lagos State and in any other state with similar provisions in the Administration of Estate Law.

8.3 Residuary clause of the High Court Law of Northern Nigeria

A significant aspect of the decision in *Cole v. Cole* that is often overlooked is the fact that it was decided based on the residuary clause of the Supreme Court Ordinance. The law that is regarded as most similar to this law is the High Court Laws in Nigeria. This is in terms of its provisions on choice of law. An example is contained in S.34 (3) & (4) of the High Court Laws of Kwara State which states:

(3) No party shall be entitled to claim benefits of any customary law if it shall appear either from the express contract or from the nature of the transaction out of which any suit or question may have arisen, that such party agreed that its obligations in connection with such transactions shall be regulated exclusively by English law or that such transactions are transactions unknown to customary law.

(4) In cases where no express rule is applicable to any matter in controversy, the court shall be governed by the principles of justice, equity and good conscience.

Although the application of law to the extent to which it was used to resolve the dispute in *Cole v. Cole* has not been disputed as to its consequences, it is the consequential effect in subsequent cases that have been contested (Salacuse, 1964).

It has also been suggested that the courts in determining whether the residuary clause should be the basis of excluding the application of customary law to the estate of an intestate, should consider whether the consequences of such a decision will not create an inequitable result since the overriding objective of the clause is to prevent injustice by subjecting a transaction to customary law. Therefore, if greater injustice will arise from the application of English law, it should not be applied.

It should however be emphasized that what is being proposed is not an outright departure from the well-established principle governing intestate succession in statutory or Christian marriages, but the restriction of its application in situations where it will result in unfair consequences such as denial of the rights of inheritance of children who have legitimate rights to inherit, since denying such children will amount to granting children of statutory marriages a status that is higher than that of children or issues of customary marriage.

Although, *Coleman v. Shang* (1959) stands as good law in this regard, the exception it created to the general rule in *Cole v. Cole* has not been adequately applied by the courts even when the material facts of the case make its application more appropriate than *Cole v. Cole*.

9. CONCLUSION

One of the inherent characteristics of plural legal systems is conflict of laws. This challenge is also reflected in Nigerian legal system. One of the ways by which this is manifested is in the choice of applicable law in intestate succession to the estate of a person subject to customary law but who has also contracted a statutory marriage.

It is fairly settled that a statutory marriage excludes the application of customary law based on the reasoning in *Cole v. Cole* which is the *locus classicus* on the matter. This approach amounts to an over-simplification of the case and a neglect of other contexts which bear close similarity to it but which are fundamentally different. Hence, it does not appear to be an inappropriate authority in all situations.

Thus, in a multi-tiered marriage, where it involves the distribution of the estate of an individual who contracts a valid customary marriage and a statutory marriage, the dispute adopts a conflict of law coloration. Hence, the tradition of resolving such disputes through conflict of law rules as demonstrated in *Coleman v. Shang*, which states that the status of children and their rights to inherit should be determined by the law under which the marriage was contracted. Therefore, issues of succession and marriage should be separated; the existence of a statutory marriage will not automatically exclude the application of customary law. The conflict of law rules in relation to succession are designed to guarantee that the estate of a deceased will be administered by the system of law which governed his life while alive. This principle has been the cornerstone of conflict of law and in particular choice of applicable law in intestate succession. It is therefore not surprising that the earliest exceptions to *Cole v. Cole* were intended to achieve this result.

Notwithstanding the fact that there have been several well-established attempts at evaluating the contexts to which *Cole v. Cole* should be applied, it continues to be treated as an over-riding authority by courts and applied without regard to the challenges of applying it to cases where the deceased has contracted other valid customary law marriages prior to or after contracting the statutory marriage.

What has generally been recommended particularly given the decision of the Privy Council in *Coleman v. Sheng* is that resort should once again be made to conflict of law rules. This resulted in the proposition that, while English law can still govern the distribution of the estate, determination of the eligibility of children to the estate should be governed by the personal law of the deceased, which would in most instances be customary law.

Although the adoption of this approach will go a long way in preventing recent emerging trends where legitimate children are denied their rights simply because their father contracted a statutory marriage, this alternative route is also not likely to be

without challenges. This is because relying on case law, which can be subject of differing interpretation denies the opportunity of certainty and precision that a legislative intervention will bring to bear on the issue. It is for this reason, that legislative intervention or law reform remains the more reliable measure. It will reduce reliance on judicial interpretation which has so far not been able to follow a clear pattern resulting in inconsistencies in the application of existing authorities on the case.

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